

The Effect of Dual Role Conflict and Job Stress on the Performance of Female Employees at the Pekanbaru City Health Office

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ABSTRACT

The Purpose of this study was to determine the effect of Dual Role Conflict and Job Stress on the Performance of Female Employees at the Pekanbaru City Health Office. With data analysis in this study is quantitative using multiple linear regression methods and the data is analyzed using the SPSS program. Based on the results of this research, it shows that dual role conflict has no effect on the performance of female employees at the Pekanbaru City Health Office. Meanwhile, the work stress variable affects the performance of female employees at the Pekanbaru City Health Office. Simultaneously, the dual role conflict and work stress variables have a significant effect on the performance variables of female employees at the Pekanbaru City Health Office. The R Square value of 0.300 or 30% means that the female employee performance variable is influenced by dual role conflict and work stress while the remaining 70% is influenced by other variables not used in this study.

INTRODUCTION

Women who are actively working face difficulties in carrying out their role as a wife and function as a mother, especially in nurturing, caring, educating, and providing love to their children as a whole. Role conflict arises when a working woman faces conflicts between her responsibilities and the tasks she must perform. For example, a nurse working the night shift may have to sacrifice time with the children at home. This is due to the duality of roles she has as a worker and as part of the family, which can sometimes interfere with daily activities and concentration at work. In addition to fulfilling obligations at home, working women must also complete their work duties and responsibilities. Both roles demand equal performance. If a woman prioritizes her work more, she may have to sacrifice time for her family. Conversely, if she focuses more on her family, her performance at work may be affected Ermawati (2016).

Women in carrying out their work often experience stress, because those who hold many roles and demands face mental pressure and tension which leads to a decrease in the level of performance of the woman. Work stress is a state of tension that creates physical and psychological imbalance, impacting the emotions, thought processes, and condition of an employee. In this context, the pressure comes from the work environment in which the employee operates. Work stress characterizes the feeling of pressure or burden experienced by employees when facing work tasks Mangkunegara (2005).

Work stress is very influential in employee performance, when employees are able to serve all the needs of visitors effectively, female employees have good performance, it will produce satisfaction at work but when female employees are unable to serve the needs of visitors, it affects the performance of these employees and therefore the aspect that needs to be considered by an agency, especially within the health service, is employee

performance, because this work is related to community service so that employee performance becomes very important. Because basically every agency wants good employee performance, so as to produce quality work, with good individual quality that must produce good performance results as well.

The impact of job stress has such a large impact that it triggers various physical, mental, and even organizational output problems. The achievement of individual employee performance is often a reflection of the successful performance of a company. Therefore, the company hopes that employees are able to show optimal performance. Because good or bad employee performance can have a significant impact on the overall performance and success of the company **Japlani (2020)**.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Definition of Human Resource Management

According to **Mangkunegara (2017)** Human Resource Management (HRM) can be defined as a series of activities that include planning, organizing, implementing, and supervising aspects such as procurement, development, rewarding, integrating, maintaining, and separating the workforce. All of these activities are directed at achieving organizational goals effectively and efficiently in managing the potential and contributions of human resources.

Human Resource Management (HRM) can be defined as a process that aims to utilize Human Resources (HR) effectively and efficiently through planning, mobilizing, and controlling activities. This process includes all the values that become human power, directed to achieve organizational goals. Thus, HRM is related to efforts to manage human potential in achieving optimal results for the success and achievement of organizational goals **Sedarmayanti (2017)**.

B. Definition of Performance

According to **Mangkunegara (2016)**, employee performance refers to the results of a person's work both in terms of quality and quantity that has been achieved in carrying out tasks in accordance with the responsibilities given. According to **Kasmir (2016)** also argues that performance is the result of work and work behavior achieved in completing the tasks and responsibilities given in a certain period.

C. Definition of Dual Role Conflict

According to **Greenhause and Beutell (1985)** dual role conflict is one of the forms of interrole conflict, namely pressure or role imbalance between roles at work and roles in the family. This usually occurs when individuals try to meet the demands of roles at work and these efforts are influenced by the individual's ability to meet the demands of his family or vice versa. Fulfillment of role demands in the family is influenced by the person's ability to meet demands with pressure stemming from excessive workload and time such as work that must be completed in a hurry and deadlines while family demands relate to the time needed to handle household tasks. Family demands are determined by the size of the family, family composition and the number of family members who are dependent on other members.

D. Definition of Work Stress

According to **Rivai (2009)** work stress can be defined as a condition of tension that creates a physical and psychological imbalance, which affects the emotions, thought processes, and conditions of an employee. According to **Handoko (2011)**, stress is a condition of tension that affects a person's emotions, thought processes, and conditions. Therefore, it can be concluded that work stress is a pressure that affects a person's physical condition in dealing with work, which makes a person feel uneasy when carrying out their activities. According to **Prabu (2016)** defines work stress as a feeling of pressure or a sense of pressure experienced by employees in dealing with their work.

E. Conceptual Framework

METHOD

Data analysis in quantitative research is a process carried out after collecting information from all respondents or other data sources. The population in this study were married female employees at the pekanbaru city health department office, the sampling technique used was purposive sampling. Purposive sampling is a sampling technique by determining certain criteria . The variables used in this study are: dual role conflict (X1), work stress (X2), and female employee performance (Y).

For testing in this study, used:

- 1. Data Quality Test**
 - a. Test of Validity
 - b. Test of Reliability
- 2. Classical Assumption Test**
 - a. Data Normality Test
 - b. Multicollinearity Test
 - c. Heteroscedasticity Test
- 3. Data Analysis Test**
 - a. Multiple Linear Analysis
 - b. Partial Test (T Test)
 - c. Simultaneous Test (F Test)
 - d. Test Coefficient of Determination (R2)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

- 1. Data Quality**
 - a. Test Validity

Table 1. Test Validity

Statement Item	Question Item	r Count	r Table	Description
Dual Role Conflict (X1)	X1.1	0,487	0,361	Valid
	X1.2	0,487	0,361	Valid
	X1.3	0,638	0,361	Valid
	X1.4	0,638	0,361	Valid
	X1.5	0,428	0,361	Valid
	X1.6	0,405	0,361	Valid
Work Stress (X2)	X2.1	0,604	0,361	Valid
	X2.2	0,432	0,361	Valid
	X2.3	0,584	0,361	Valid
	X2.4	0,645	0,361	Valid
	X2.5	0,680	0,361	Valid

Statement Item	Question Item	r Count	r Table	Description
	X2.6	0,374	0,361	Valid
	X2.7	0,470	0,361	Valid
	X2.8	0,458	0,361	Valid
	X2.9	0,400	0,361	Valid
	X2.10	0,462	0,361	Valid
	X2.11	0,376	0,361	Valid
	X2.12	0,483	0,361	Valid
Female Employee Performance (Y)	Y.1	0,532	0,361	Valid
	Y.2	0,734	0,361	Valid
	Y.3	0,734	0,361	Valid
	Y.4	0,796	0,361	Valid
	Y.5	0,677	0,361	Valid
	Y.6	0,515	0,361	Valid
	Y.7	0,576	0,361	Valid
	Y.8	0,770	0,361	Valid
	Y.9	0,770	0,361	Valid
	Y.10	0,708	0,361	Valid
	Y.11	0,524	0,361	Valid
	Y.12	0,484	0,361	Valid
	Y.13	0,650	0,361	Valid
	Y.14	0,628	0,361	Valid
	Y.15	0,372	0,361	Valid
	Y.16	0,404	0,361	Valid

Source: Processed Data, 2024

Judging from table 1 of the validity test recapitulation results, it can be stated that the measuring instrument used in this study is declared valid or capable of measuring the phenomenon under study, with the results for each questionnaire statement per variable it can be seen that the Corrected item total correlation value is greater than 0.361. This shows that the data has met the assumptions of the validity test and can be used in further regression analysis.

b. Test of Reliability

Table 2. Test Reliability

Variabel	Cronbach's Alpha	Sign	Value	Conclusion
Dual Role Conflict (X1)	0,689	>	0,60	Reliabel
Work Stress (X2)	0,722	>	0,60	Reliabel
Female Employee Performance (Y)	0,886	>	0,60	Reliabel

Source: Processed Data, 2024

Judging from table 2 above, it can be seen that the reliability value of Dual Role Conflict is 0.689, Work Stress is 0.722 and Female Employee Performance is 0.886 where Cronbach's Alpha of all variables > 0.6, meaning that the measuring instrument used in this study is reliable or trustworthy.

2. Classical Assumption Test

a. Data Normality Test

Normality test is a test carried out to determine the distribution of data whether the data is normally distributed or not in a variable or group. If the graph is normally distributed it will form a straight diagonal

line. According to Ghozali (2018) the way to see whether the data is normally distributed or not is as follows:

1. The regression model completes the normality assumption if the data spreads around the diagonal line and follows the line direction.
2. Regression that does not complete the assumption of normality if the data does not follow the direction of the diagonal line or the data spreads far from the diagonal line.

Picture 2. P P Plot

b Multicollinearity Test

Table 3. Test of Multicollinierity

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	118.754	15.297		7.763	<,001		
X1	-1.062	.527	-.325	-2.014	.054	.997	1.003
X2	-.642	.243	-.425	-2.637	.014	.997	1.003

Source: Processed Data, 2024

Judging from table 3, it can be concluded that the multicollinearity test of the Dual Role Conflict (X1) and Work Stress (X2) variables does not have multicollinearity, because the results of the multicollinearity test show that the VIF value of the variable Dual role conflict (X1) and work stress (X2) is $1.003 < 10$ and the Tolerance value is $0.997 > 0.1$, so there is no indication of multicollinearity in the regression model in the research conducted.

c. Heteroscedasticity Test

The purpose of the heteroscedasticity test is to measure whether in the regression model there is an inequality of variance from the residuals of one observation to another. If the significance value is > 0.05, the regression model does not occur heteroscedasticity Ghozali (2018).

This test is carried out by looking at a certain pattern on the graph where the Y axis is the predicted one and the X axis is the residuals that have been standardized. The basic basis for decision making, below:

1. If there is a certain pattern such as the existing points forming a regular pattern (wavy widening then narrowing).
2. If no clear pattern is found and the points spread above and below the number 0 on the Y axis, there is no heteroscedasticity.

Picture 3. Scatter Plot

From the test results above, it is concluded that there is no clear pattern on the scatterplot, so there is no Heteroscedasticity problem. meets the assumptions of the validity test and can be used in further regression analysis.

3. Data Analysis Test

a. Multiple Linear Analysis

Table 4. Regression Analysis

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	118.754	15.297		7.763	<,001
	Dual Role Conflict (X1)	-1.062	.527	-.325	-2.014	.054
	Work Stress (X2)	-.642	.243	-.425	-2.637	.014

Source: Processed Data, 2024

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e$$

$$Y = 118.754 - 1.062 X_1 - 0.205 X_2 + e$$

Based on the regression equation above, it can be explained as follows:

1. The constant value (α) of 118.754 means that if the dual role conflict and work stress are assumed to be zero (0) then the performance of female employees remains at 118.752.
2. The regression coefficient value of the dual role conflict variable (X1) is -1.062. The X1 coefficient value is negative, meaning that if the dual role conflict increases by one unit, the performance of female employees (Y) will decrease by -1.062. And if the dual role conflict decreases by one unit, the performance of female employees (Y) will increase by 1.062.
3. The regression coefficient value of the work stress variable (X2) is -0.642. The coefficient value of X1 is negative, meaning that if work stress increases by one unit, the performance of female employees (Y) will decrease by -0.642. And if work stress decreases by one unit, the performance of female employees (Y) will increase by 0.642.
4. Standard error (e) is a random variable and has a probability distribution that represents all factors that have an influence on Y but are not included in the equation.

b. Partial Test (T Test)

Table 5. T Test

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	118.754	15.297		7.763	<,001
	Dual Role Conflict (X1)	-1.062	.527	-.325	-2.014	.054
	Work Stress (X2)	-.642	.243	-.425	-2.637	.014

Source: Processed Data, 2024

1. Based on the t-test table above, it is known that the significance value of the dual role conflict variable (X1) is $0.054 > 0.05$ and the tcount in the T-test coefficients table is $2.014 < 2.051$. So it can be concluded that H0 is accepted, which means that the Dual Role Conflict variable (X1) does not significantly affect the Performance of Female Employees (Y) at the Pekanbaru City Health Office.
2. Based on the t-test table above, it is known that the significance value of the Work Stress variable (X2) is $0.014 < 0.05$ and the t count in the T-test coefficients table is $2.637 > 2.051$. So it can be concluded that H2 is accepted, which means that the Work Stress variable (X2) has a significant effect on the Performance of Female Employees (Y) at the Pekanbaru City Health Office.

c. Simultaneous Test (F Test)

Table 6. F Test

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	212.957	2	106.479	5.791	.008 ^b
	Residual	496.410	27	18.386		
	Total	709.367	29			

Source: Processed Data, 2024

Based on the t-test table above, it is known that the significance value is $0.008 < 0.05$ and the fcount in the F test coefficients table is $5,791 > 3.34$. So it can be concluded that H0 is rejected and H3 is accepted, which means that simultaneously the Dual Role Conflict and Work Stress variables have a significant influence on the performance of female employees at the Pekanbaru City Health Office.

d. Test Coefficient of Determination (R²)**Table 7. Coefficient of Determination**

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.548 ^a	.300	.248	4.28784

Source: Processed Data, 2024

Based on table 7, it can be concluded that the correlation value (R) obtained is 0.548 and it can be concluded that there is an influence between the independent and dependent variables. The R square value of 0.300 or 30% indicates that the effect of dual role conflict in influencing the performance of female employees is 30%, while the remaining 70% is influenced by other variables that are not included and not used by researchers in this study.

CONCLUSION

This study aims to examine the effect of dual role conflict and job stress on the performance of female employees at the Pekanbaru City Health Office. Based on the results of statistical analysis and discussion, the conclusions that can be drawn are as follows:

1. Dual role conflict does not affect the performance of female employees at the Pekanbaru City Health Office. That is, the research shows that the performance of female employees remains good, regardless of the presence or absence of dual role conflict. This is due to the good emotional maturity possessed by female employees, as well as supported by factors of age, length of service, level of education, and ability to carry out the role of employee and housewife, so that both roles can be carried out properly.
2. Conversely, job stress affects the performance of female employees. This is due to the tasks, roles and responsibilities that must be completed by female employees, which sometimes cause work stress because the burden is too heavy. This stress can come from the individual, the environment, or the organization.

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